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USE OF SIMULATION FOR CHEMOTHERAPY COMPETENCY TRAINING

A DOCTORAL PROJECT

Submitted in Partial Fulfillment of the Requirements

For the degree of

DOCTOR OF NURSING PRACTICE

By

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ABSTRACT

Chemotherapy is classified as a high-alert and hazardous drug by the National Institute for Occupational Safety and Health (OSHA). The American Society of Clinical Oncology (ASCO) and the Oncology Nursing Society (ONS) are the two organizations that recently revised the ONS Chemotherapy and Immunotherapy Certification Course curriculum in 2019 for oncology nurses. This revision included a shift from an in-person process, to one that is now fully online as a self-learning module. An increase in chemotherapy administration errors was noted this past year in newly certified oncology nurses at this DNP project site, who had completed this online certification process. Reports of low confidence and confidence levels were reported by these nurses, when administering these high-alert medications. The purpose of this DNP quality improvement study was to assess whether the use of chemotherapy administration simulation training would have any effect on confidence and competency levels in newly certified oncology nurses. Eleven nurses participated in two chemotherapy administration simulation experiences during November 2020. The entire group of participants improved their scores on a self-confidence and competency tool upon completion of the two simulations and debriefing sessions, using pre- and post-testing measurements. The next steps are to observe whether the number of chemotherapy administration errors of these newly certified oncology nurses differs from that of the previous year.

Keywords: chemotherapy administration, competence, confidence, simulation

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Background

The National Institute for Occupational Safety and Health has identified chemotherapy as a high-alert and hazardous drug. Accordingly, the American Society of Clinical Oncology (ASCO) and the Oncology Nursing Society (ONS) (2013) have developed chemotherapy administration safety standard. Although cancer treatments including chemotherapy have significantly prolonged the lifespan of oncology patients, the administration of these toxic, yet lifesaving agents, require extensive knowledge and experience to ensure safe care (Carreon et al., 2015). As of 2013, the Oncology Nursing Society requires nurses who administer chemotherapy, immunotherapy, and biotherapy to complete an online module that includes an open-book multiple choice test conducted through their course site. The curriculum includes chemotherapy regimens, chemotherapy calculations and verification of orders, safe handling, administration, spill management and patient outcomes (Olsen et al., 2019).

Historically, nurses were certified in a classroom environment that included both didactic and hands-on experience. While the online module on chemotherapy is thorough, learning this type of information without any hands-on practice to accompany it may not be the best teaching and learning strategy. This shift in the certification process has negatively affected nursing confidence and potentially competency at the local practice setting of this DNP author.

Significance

Nurses newly certified in chemotherapy administration have reported a lack of confidence and competence when administering chemotherapy drugs in an acute care hospital in Los Angeles County. During 2018 and 2019, there was an increase in chemotherapy medication errors related to wrong route, incorrect administration and delayed administration of rescue medication for hypersensitivity reactions. A significant finding was that each of these adverse

events was made by a nurse who had been newly certified within that past year. In communicating with these nurses, they reported feeling anxious when receiving assignments that included administering chemotherapy, as they were worried about making a mistake that would harm their patients.

Today's education environment is experiencing an increased use of online teaching. An advantage of this approach is that educational modules are readily accessible whenever and wherever the learners wish to access them. Additionally, learners can take their time completing the module. One of the limitations with this approach is that often no real time face-to-face interaction occurs with an instructor. Another limitation is that while there may be a virtual hands-on learning experience, there is no actual real time hands-on training (kinetic skills-based learning) experience. According to Su and Juestel (2010), it is challenging to evaluate critical thinking and psychomotor skills through the use of online modules. In deciding how best to teach and certify nurses on administering high-risk drugs such as chemotherapy, one must consider the teaching and learning ramifications judiciously.

Various teaching strategies in nursing education have evolved over the years, with simulation receiving increased attention. Simulation as a teaching strategy is highly effective and integrates the principles of adult learning theory (Kuhrik et al., 2008). Adult learners process concepts best, by being able to apply new knowledge into practice (Knowles, 1998). Simulation creates an artificial environment that feels like reality to the learner. Simulation can be done through the use of a standardized patient, a manikin or by use of role-play. Nurse educators are able to evaluate how novice nurses apply the new knowledge in a simulated patient situation (Gatti-Petito et al., 2013). By being able to practice nursing skills or scenarios in a simulated

setting that replicates working with real patients, the learner's confidence and competence can often be increased (Gatti-Petito et al., 2013).

Purpose Statement

The purpose of this Doctor of Nursing Practice (DNP) project is to increase nurse confidence and competence when administering chemotherapy drugs at an acute care hospital, by including simulation as part of the chemotherapy certification process for its facility's oncology nurses.

Project Objectives

The goal of this DNP project is to improve the confidence and competence of oncology nurses related to chemotherapy administration on an oncology unit. To meet this goal, the author will:

1. Develop two simulations related to chemotherapy.
2. Pilot these simulations with a group of 12 newly certified chemotherapy nurses.
3. Evaluate the efficacy of these simulations on nursing confidence and competency.

Supporting Framework

Implementing practice change may be a complex process especially in a fast-paced environment like an acute care facility. However, incorporating the use of conceptual model strengthens the potential for success. Kurt Lewin's (1947) Three-Step Model will guide the practice change of incorporating simulation as part of the hospital's chemotherapy certification program (see Figure 1). Lewin summarized this Three-Step Model as a process that will lead to a successful behavioral change because of three essential stages: unfreezing, change, and freezing. Kurt Lewin was a widely recognized child psychologist who devoted his research to social

conflict change theories. Field Theory was created by Lewin in the 1920s and served as the core for his Three-Step Model (Burnes, 2020).

First published in 1947, Lewin's model has been argued as being one of the most influential models for creating a behavioral change (Bartunek & Woodman, 2015; Cummings et al., 2015). The Three-Step Model has been referenced in multiple and diverse types of project changes. Evans et al., (2016) used the Three-Step Model as their framework when their cancer institute initiated and piloted a "Medical Orders for Life-Sustaining Treatment" (MOLST) form. Tetef (2017) also used Lewin's model in conjunction with Roger's diffusion of innovations theory when their Southern California facility first implemented their new bronchial thermoplasty program. Finally, Lewin's Three-Step Model was recently utilized as an evidence-based approach to change the way that newborns were being weighed at an academic medical center (Pickerel et al., 2020).

The first step of Lewin's Three-Step Model is "unfreezing." Unfreezing is defined as preparing the organization for the need of change (Shirey, 2013). This stage may be challenging, as it requires the change agent to marshal others like leadership and frontline nursing staff to support the need for change. Destabilizing the equilibrium is the first key step in getting key stakeholders to understand and experience a sense of urgency for change.

Conducting a gap analysis, providing a description of a harmful event, or presenting evidence and data are a few recommended strategies to disrupt the equilibrium (Shirey, 2013). Concerns or issues are commonly brought up by stakeholders during this stage; however, the change agent must always understand these concerns and respond appropriately. Once support is obtained from leadership and frontline staff, planning how to implement change can then begin. Lewin's first step will apply to this DNP project by first constructing a committee that will

include a director, the oncology nurse manager, the oncology nurse educator, charge nurses, pharmacists, and staff nurses. The committee will gather data, present the need for change, conduct a literature review, and design the plan for change.

The second step of the model is “change,” which is sometimes referred to as “moving” or “transitioning” (Burnes, 2020; Cummings et al., 2015; Shirey, 2013). The change agent(s) will be active in this stage, once behavioral or psychological change is actually occurring. According to Lewin (1947), moving has started when the forces pressing for change exceeds the forces resisting change. This stage has been found to be difficult to predict because of the conflicting forces (Burnes, 2020). However, it is crucial to identify and control key variables in the change process. Communication and time are key variables in this stage. Lewin’s second step will be applied to this DNP project by carrying out audits, holding committee meetings, and consistently communicating consistently with the oncology staff nurses via meetings, huddles, and emails.

Lastly, the third stage of Lewin’s Three-Step Model is “refreezing,” or what is sometimes referred to as “freezing” (Burnes, 2020; Cummings & Worley, 2015). Lewin (1947), describes this stage as constructing the new process or permanent situation. Regression back to old practices is a limitation of any change process; however, change agents must develop a plan to prevent this from happening to ensure sustainability of the practice change. Preventing regression can be supported by rewarding adherence for those who are either practicing the new change and by incorporating it into organizational policies (Burnes, 2020; Shirley, 2013). Lewin’s third stage will be operationalized in this DNP project by updating the unit’s chemotherapy administration policy, initiating audits, providing in-services, modifying online and face-to-face education, and conducting staff meetings to maintain permanence of the new change.

Figure 1

Lewin's Three-Step Model

Note. Permission to reproduce this model has been obtained (Appendix A)

Review of Literature

A literature review was conducted utilizing the databases: PubMed, CINAHL, EBSCO, SAGE Journals, ScienceDirect, and Cochrane Library. Search terms and a combination of these terms included “medication administration,” “nursing competency,” “nursing confidence,” “oncology nurse,” “self-efficacy,” “simulation,” “simulation administration,” and “simulation measurement.” All research was screened for inclusion and exclusion criteria. The inclusion criteria included English language, scholarly journals, and being published between 2008-2020. Exclusion criteria included research articles on the desired topic that were not related to nursing. To accomplish this, the literature was focused on the following four major content areas: simulation in nursing education, confidence after simulation, competency in medication administration, and simulation for chemotherapy administration.

Simulation in Nursing Education

Nurse educators are continually trying to find new and creative teaching strategies to promote the effective learning of various nursing skills, including critical thinking, and better communication. Simulation has been introduced in nursing education as an effective teaching strategy to promote the development of such nursing skills (Norman, 2012). According to Arthur et al. (2012), simulation is an educational tool that provides a realistic yet safe clinical situation for the learner. According to Lavoie & Clarke (2017), simulation provides nurses with the means to realistically practice and institute interventions in an artificial setting, which has been shown to enhance their learning. Simulation can be done utilizing manikins or standardized patients, through virtual means, or with role-playing amongst the learners themselves. In fact, simulation has been increasingly utilized in nursing education, as schools have experienced decreased access to clinical facilities in recent years.

Debriefing is arguably the most important part of the simulation experience in terms of teaching strategies, and is defined as a phase after simulation to reflect and analyze the simulation experience (Alhaj Ali & Musallam, 2018). Learners can reflect and analyze the simulation experience by synthesizing their feelings and ideas. Debriefing allows the learners to critically self-reflect on their simulation experience, performance, skills and attitudes (Neil & Wotton, 2011; Shinnick et al., 2011). The National League for Nursing (NLN) and the International Nursing Association for Clinical Simulation and Learning have emphasized that debriefing is a core component of simulation-based learning (Alhaj Ali & Mussalam, 2018; Meakim et al., 2013; NLN, 2015).

Despite its importance, it should be noted that debriefing after simulations is frequently missed, thus decreasing the efficacy of that simulation (Alhaj Ali & Musallam, 2018). The recommended amount of time for debriefing should match or exceed the time of the actual simulation scenario (Reed et al., 2013; Royle & Hargiss, 2015). While it is recommended that the instructors serve as a facilitator during the discussion, it is the learners who should reflect on the simulation activity and verbally share their thoughts.

GAS (Gathering, Analyzing and Summarization) debriefing method is a structured framework that has been widely used in hospital learning environments after a simulation. American Heart Association first pioneered the GAS method after their simulation scenarios (Freytag et al., 2017). The first phase of the GAS method is gathering where participants gather together as a group and express their thoughts and feeling about the simulation. Analyzing is the next phase. The participants discuss the simulation, reflect on the objectives, and then analyze their actions during the simulation. Lastly, the participants and debriefing facilitator summarize the discussion or simulation experience. Overall, the GAS approach has been found to induce

learning and encourage the participants to share their thoughts and feelings of their simulation experience (Freitag et al., 2017; Ozekcin et al., 2015)¹ For this DNP project, GAS debriefing will be utilized after each simulation with the course instructors facilitating this phase.

Confidence Building with Simulation

Nursing has rapidly changed to a high-skilled and demanding profession to meet the needs of higher acuity patients (NLN, 2015). Nurse educators strive to ensure their nurses or students find their learning experiences as being effective and also results in them feeling more confident about their practice, which is why NLN endorsed simulation as an essential teaching strategy (Zapko et al., 2018).

One nursing program in Ohio studied their students' level of confidence, after having them go through repeated simulations throughout the nursing program. This was a two-year longitudinal descriptive study that utilized a convenience sampling methodology. The authors found that repeated simulations significantly increased the confidence levels, as self-reported by their 199 nursing student participants (Zapko et al., 2018). This DNP project will be looking at levels of confidence amongst its newly certified oncology nurses, by comparing degree of confidence both before and following two different chemotherapy administrations simulations.

Deteriorating patient scenarios can affect one's level of confidence when they are expected to intervene quickly and appropriately (Crowe et al., 2018). One simulation center in Kentucky evaluated self-efficacy, after 69 nursing students experienced a critical post-partum hemorrhaging high fidelity patient (Weiler et al. 2018). The authors reported a statistically significant increase in critical thinking skills and self-confidence of $p < 0.05$. A Canadian facility used simulation as part of their deteriorating patient course for the purpose of increasing their nurses' confidence. The authors found a significant increase in nursing confidence and

knowledge as compared to their pre-survey or baseline scores (Crowe et al., 2018). Multiple facilities have implemented simulation when teaching has involved deteriorating patients (from medical-surgical to critical care cases) and all found significant increases in confidence (Bell-Gordon et al., 2014; Boiling & Hardin-Pierce, 2016; Liaw et al., 2014). This DNP project will additionally be examining levels of confidence in their newly certified oncology nurses by evaluating them post simulation, using an evidenced-based confidence survey.

Simulation and Medication Administration

Simulation is commonly used to increase nursing competency for skills that require a high level of competence. Medication administration is a complex skill in which all nurses need to be competent (Joint Commission, 2020). A nursing faculty in Illinois compared the effectiveness of using simulation as a means for measuring nursing competency, versus the traditional classroom when teaching medication administration. Eighty-five baccalaureate nursing students were randomly divided between the two groups and a significant increase in competency was observed in the intervention group (Jarvill et al., 2018). Another nursing program utilized standardized patient and manikins for their medication administration simulation and found that 98-100% of the nursing students improved their medication administration skills (Ham, 2016). While both studies were piloted at their respective nursing programs and perhaps not generalizable to other nursing schools, they still suggest that simulation may be an effective teaching strategy for medication administration competencies.

The Joint Commission (2020) and Institute of Medicine (IOM) (2006a) reported that medication errors can be decreased by eliminating distractions during medication administration. Since distractions are not entirely preventable, it is essential that nurses learn how to respond safely and appropriately to distractions during medication administration (IOM, 2006a; Thomas

et al., 2014; Treiber & Jones, 2012). One nursing faculty in Indiana implemented distractions like alarms and music during multiple medication administration simulations (Thomas et al., 2014). They found that the nursing students made medication errors in their first simulation, but were able to then acknowledge their errors and discuss how to prevent errors in future simulations. Of note is the fact that the authors did find significant improvements in safely administering medications, despite the presence of distractions in the students' second simulation (Thomas et al., 2014).

Using Simulation for Chemotherapy Administration

A review of the literature produced four articles that specifically linked the use of simulation with chemotherapy administration. These studies focused on patient safety, nurse competence, or the medication administration procedure itself. In the article by Crannell (2012), the author utilized simulation to examine oncology nurses' knowledge of the entire chemotherapy process, including order verification, safe handling, administration and spill management practices. Meuhlbauer et al. (2013) studied nurse competency with chemotherapy on a medical-surgical unit where oncology patients were only sporadically placed there. The other two publications involved safety aspects of chemotherapy administration. One study examined administration of the specific chemotherapeutic drug, Vincristine (Corbitt et al. 2017). Lastly, one article focused on pediatric oncology patients and used simulation to teach both staff registered nurses and student nurses (Linnard-Palmer, 2012).

Summary

Over the past decade, there have been numerous studies on the use of simulation in nursing education. The older publications used simulation as a means for improving patient care, communication skills or reviewing medication administration methods. Some of the simulation

studies within the past five years have been geared towards fostering better interprofessional collaboration practices. While meta-analyses and systematic reviews on simulation were found, they were not specific to oncology nursing, nursing confidence or nursing competence.

The literature strongly supports the efficacy of simulation to improve confidence and competence within nursing practice. Simulation not only provides opportunities for practicing complex skills such as medication administration; it is viewed as a useful strategy for evaluating nursing competence with decision making and actual performance. Based on a desire to decrease medication administration errors by newly certified oncology nurses at the site of this DNP project, a search on the topic was conducted.

A limited number of publications were found that specifically relate to improving nursing competence and safety when administering chemotherapy. Three of the articles were published approximately eight years ago, and one was published in 2017. Although each of these articles contributed to the existing literature, each had aspects that made their study different from this current DNP quality improvement project. No publications were found that connected simulation and level of confidence with chemotherapy administration. As a result of finding a gap in the literature, this DNP project will examine confidence and competence with chemotherapy administration among newly certified chemotherapy nurses who work on an adult oncology unit, using simulation as an educational strategy.

Methods

The purpose of this Doctor of Nursing Practice (DNP) project was to increase nurse confidence and competence when administering chemotherapy drugs at an acute care hospital, by adding simulation as part of the chemotherapy certification process for its facility's oncology nurses. Participants completed the required ONS Chemotherapy/Immunotherapy Course online module and attended a four-hour in-person review course. This review course involved having staff nurses participate in two different simulation exercises.

Design

A quality improvement approach was utilized for this DNP project. This approach was selected because of an increase in chemotherapy administration errors by nurses on an oncology unit who had been recently certified to give chemotherapy drugs to their patients. The project was also in response to reports of high-anxiety and fear of not providing safe care when administering or handling chemotherapy by these same newly chemotherapy certified oncology nurses.

Participants

All newly certified chemotherapy nurses as of July 2020, were mandated to participate in this pilot chemotherapy simulation course per the director of oncology services. Participants were informed about this requirement through hospital flyers (see Appendix B) and work emails (see Appendix C). Hospital flyers were posted in the oncology unit nursing lounges and emailed to eligible participants, oncology charge nurses, a clinical oncology pharmacist, the director of oncology services, and oncology nurse manager. Eligibility criteria included nurses who are employed at the project facility, had completed the ONS Chemotherapy and Immunotherapy Course within one year of the project initiation, and provide care to patients 18 years of age and

older who have been diagnosed with cancer. Eleven nurses participated in this simulation educational program.

Setting

This quality improvement project occurred at a non-profit, 380-bed community acute care facility located in Los Angeles County. This facility has a designated 26-bed oncology medical-surgical unit, although there are chemotherapy certified nurses throughout the hospital to meet the needs of these critical care patients. The simulation experience took place in the facility's simulation center. This center has three available rooms that were made to replicate a patient's room. It also has a classroom where the debriefing session was held, following each of the two simulation exercises. A clinical simulation skills technician assisted with the scenarios. High-fidelity manikins were used as the patients and controlled by the clinical simulation skills technician. Permission to implement this project was approved by the director of oncology services (see Appendix D).

Ethical Considerations

This project was initiated after being approved by the California State University, Fullerton (CSUF) and Torrance Memorial Medical Center Institutional Review Board. As this is a quality improvement project that requires all newly chemotherapy certified staff nurses to participate in an educational training, it was deemed as exempt. Participant characteristics were not reported or collected, to ensure privacy and confidentiality of the nurses. Nurses who went through this simulation training received four hours of pay from the hospital's elective education account.

Procedures

Simulations were incorporated in the facility's chemotherapy certification program based on the *2013 ASCO/ONS Chemotherapy Administration Safety Standards*. Simulations were created and evaluated by four content experts, an oncology nurse educator, two oncology charge registered nurses, and a clinical oncology pharmacist. Content experts were established and consisted of the oncology nurse educator, two oncology charge nurses, and a clinical oncology pharmacist. The content experts reviewed the simulation objectives, narrative and evaluation prior to the course. Simulations were revised according to feedback from the experts. An educational plan was then presented to the hospital's cancer committee. Oncology nurses required to attend the simulation course were notified through flyers, emails, staff announcements and manager recommendations August-September 2020.

Nurses enrolled in the course using the API Link found on the flyer. Two simulation scenarios were developed and approved by content experts (see Appendix F). Evaluators or content experts practiced evaluating competency using the *Competency Evaluation Form* through the use of videos for 2 hours. Clinical Simulation Skill Tech was contacted to schedule simulation lab on November 2, 2020, from 8:00 A. M.-12:00 P.M. and November 19, 2020, from 8:00 A.M. – 12:00 P.M. All equipment needed for simulations were gathered (see Appendix G).

On the days of the simulations, the content experts reviewed the objectives of the four-hour in-person review course with an emphasis on the purpose of the simulations. Instructions and room tours were given by this DNP author. This DNP author explained how data will be collected, project purpose, and camera in simulation rooms. The nurses had the option of completing the self-confidence portion of *National League of Nursing (NLN) Student Satisfaction and Self-Confidence in Learning* scale (see Appendix H) to assess for learners'

confidence pre-intervention. Each nurse was called by alphabetical order and assigned one out of the three patient rooms randomly. Each nurse completed simulation one for twenty minutes. Each content expert evaluated simulation two through the use of the facility's chemotherapy immunotherapy competency evaluation form (see Appendix J). This DNP author watched simulations using the simulation camera. Once the nurse completed the simulation, the nurse returned to classroom until everyone had completed simulation 1. A twenty-minute debriefing occurred with all nurses, evaluators, and DNP author using *GAS Debriefing Framework*. (see Appendix K). Questions and feedback were provided for 10 minutes.

The same format followed for simulation two. The nurses completed simulation two for twenty minutes. Each content expert evaluated simulation two through the use of the facility's chemotherapy immunotherapy competency evaluation form. This DNP author watched simulations through a camera. Once the simulation was complete, the nurse returned to classroom until everyone had participated in simulation two. Another twenty-minute debriefing occurred with all nurses, evaluators, and DNP author using *GAS Debriefing Framework*. Questions and feedback were provided for 10 minutes. Each nurse had the option of completing the self-confidence portion of *National League of Nursing (NLN) Student Satisfaction and Self-Confidence in Learning* scale (see Appendix H) to assess for learners' confidence post intervention. The content experts met the following week to analyze the scores and effectiveness of the simulation experiences.

Instruments

Two instruments were utilized for this quality improvement project. The first instrument was a post-intervention survey of confidence using the self-confidence portion of the *National League of Nursing (NLN) Student Satisfaction and Self-Confidence in Learning*. The second

instrument was the facility's chemotherapy/immunotherapy administration competency verification tool.

NLN Student Satisfaction and Self-Confidence in Learning

The NLN *Student Satisfaction and Self-Confidence in Learning Scale* (see Appendix H) was created by the NLN and Laerdal National Simulation Group in 2003 (NLN, 2020). The instrument includes five questions that measure satisfaction and eight that measure self-confidence, using a Likert Scale (Zapko et al., 2018). This instrument is a five-point scale which includes: strongly disagree, disagree, undecided, agree, and strongly agree. Only the self-confidence subscale portion was used for this DNP project. Several studies reported this tool having content validity when measuring confidence amongst learners following simulation (Wang et al., 2013; Zapko et al., 2018; Zulkosky, 2012). Franklin et al. (2014) reported Cronbach's alpha of 0.92 for the satisfaction scale and 0.83 on the self-confidence scale in regards to reliability. Confidence scores were added for each nurse pre-intervention and compared to the added score post-intervention. Permission to use and modify this tool by the National League of Nursing and Laerdal National Simulation Group has been obtained (see Appendix I).

Chemotherapy/Immunotherapy Administration Competency Verification

This instrument (see Appendix J) was established by the facility where the project was implemented. This instrument was developed based on the *ASCO/ONS chemotherapy administration safety standards* and utilized when evaluating initial and annual competency for chemotherapy certified nurses. As this is the competency evaluation form currently used by the facility, this form was used when evaluating staff chemotherapy administration competency during both simulations. This tool consists of 24 options in which a nurse can receive zero points

for not completing a step or one point for completing it, totaling a max of 24 points. Nurses must have received 24 points in their second simulation, otherwise a re-train and re-evaluation plan would be required in the near future.

Results

The purpose of this DNP project was to assess if confidence and competence levels among new oncology nurses when administering chemotherapy would be increased through the use of simulation. The simulations for this DNP project was held on November 2, 2020, and November 19, 2020, at a simulation lab in a community acute care facility located in Los Angeles County.

Participant Demographics

Participants were informed and recruited from August 2020, to November 2020. A total of eleven nurses were eligible to participate, and all eleven did participate in both of the two simulations associated with this project. Demographic data was not collected nor reported, to maintain the confidentiality and privacy of these nurses. All participants were offered the option of answering the self-confidence portion of the *National League of Nursing (NLN) Student Satisfaction and Self-Confidence in Learning* scale. All eleven nurses agreed to answer the self-confidence survey before and after both simulations.

Self-Confidence Pre-Intervention

Participants had the option to take the self-confidence portion of the *National League of Nursing (NLN) Student Satisfaction and Self-Confidence in Learning Scale* and all eleven participants agreed to answer this scale before the simulations. The maximum score representing the highest confidence is forty. The scores collected before intervention are presented in a table (see Appendix K). The lowest score was nurse eight (confidence score of 29) while the highest confidence score belonged to nurse five (confidence score of 38). The mean score for all 11 participants pre-intervention was 33, while the median score was 32.

Self-Confidence Post-Intervention

Participants had the option to take the self-confidence portion of the *National League of Nursing (NLN) Student Satisfaction and Self-Confidence in Learning Scale*, and all 11 participants agreed to complete this tool after the simulations. Scores that were collected post simulation are formatted in a table (see Appendix K) and bar graph (see Appendix L). Scores ranged from 31 to 40. Seven nurses scored the maximum self-confidence score of 40. The mean score for the 11 participants was 38.45 and the median score was 40. A difference was noted in pre-simulation versus post-simulation self-confidence scores, when comparing the scores post-simulations versus pre-simulations.

Competency Assessment Post-Simulation One

Participants were scored on their competency level in the simulation exercise using the facility's chemotherapy/ immunotherapy administration competency verification form. A maximum score of 24 was possible. The scores are formatted in a table for the 11 nurses (see Appendix M). Scores for the participants ranged from 12 to 23 after simulation 1. The mean score for the 11 participants after the first simulation was 19.27, while the median score was 20. There were no nurses who attained the maximum score.

Competency Assessment Post-Simulation Two

Participants were scored on their competency level after the second simulation using the same competency verification form. A score of 24 was required post-simulation two, or the participant would be scheduled for subsequent training and testing at a future date. The second simulation scores are formatted in a table (see Appendix M) and bar graph (see Appendix N) for the 11 participating nurses. All 11 nurses saw an improvement in their competency scores. The mean and median score after the second simulation for all 11 nurses was 24.

Discussion

The purpose of this DNP project was to increase self-confidence and competence among newly chemotherapy certified nurses through the use of simulations trainings. Eleven oncology nurses at a community acute care facility in Los Angeles County participated in this DNP project. Each participant completed a self-confidence scale before and after simulations. These participants were additionally tested on their competency level with chemotherapy administration, using the facility's chemotherapy competency verification form after simulation one and then again after simulation two. This DNP author was interested in assessing if there would be an improvement in the participants' pre- and post-simulation self-confidence scores, when comparing simulation one and two. This DNP author also wished to identify if any of these nurses would require further training and testing, since demonstrating full competency was a requirement of the facility's policy.

When comparing the scores, improvements were noted in both self-confidence and competence among all 11 participants. Each of the 11 nurses had higher self-confidence scores after simulation two, in comparison to their simulation 1 results. All of the participants demonstrated full competence, according to the facility's policy, by the end of simulation two. Nurse four improved his/her self-confidence score by one point while the other participants improved their scores by significantly more. Nurse three only attained a competency score of 12 after the first simulation, but following the debriefing process was able to get a score of 24 following the second simulation.

All 11 nurses actively participated in the simulation debriefing sessions, and the content experts additionally summarized the debriefing discussion at the end of each session. While it

would have made for an interesting finding, a relationship between the participant competence score and self-confidence score was unable to be established.

A few limitations existed with this project. The number of nurse participants was only 11, making for an extremely small sample size. A much larger sample size would be needed in order for the results to be considered significant. Another limitation for this project was that it was a pilot project for this facility. This DNP author, the content experts, and the simulation skills technician facilitated this type of project for the first time. The simulation manikin had a few technical issues during the simulations on the first day, which could have affected both the participants' confidence and competence scores. Lastly, the debriefing sessions had to be conducted using COVID-19 social distancing procedures, making some of the discussion difficult to hear by both the participants and the content experts.

Recommendations

There are a few recommendations and comments to offer, based upon this DNP project experience. Utilizing simulation for reinforcing chemotherapy administration skills and promoting self-confidence are highly recommended for those new to caring for oncology patients. Nurses learn at their own speeds and may require shorter or longer periods of practice. Second, a larger sample size needs to be used to support the belief that simulations can increase confidence and competency among newly certified nurses. Third, the costs associated with implementing simulation courses need to be considered, as all facilities do not possess a simulation lab, high-fidelity manikins, or a simulation technician. Role-play or a standardized patient have been used in lieu of a high-fidelity manikin. Lastly, simulation scenarios should be routinely evaluated and updated to keep up with current evidence-based practices.

Conclusion

The purpose of this DNP quality improvement project was to increase confidence and competence among newly certified chemotherapy nurses in a community acute care facility in Los Angeles County. This quality improvement project was implemented by this DNP author in response to the increase in chemotherapy administration errors by newly certified chemotherapy nurses. Newly certified chemotherapy nurses at this facility vocalized not feeling confident nor competent when administering chemotherapy.

The recent shift in the certification process by the Oncology Nursing Society from a classroom environment that consisted of discussions and hands-on-training to the current online self-learning module and open book exam may not be the best means of learning this nursing procedure. Simulations consisting of a high-fidelity manikin, standardized patient, or role-play have been proven to be an effective teaching strategy for healthcare workers when handling different patient scenarios.

This DNP author implemented a course for the newly certified chemotherapy nurses in her facility that required staff nurse participation in two chemotherapy administration simulation scenarios. The project results were quite promising, in that all 11 participants improved their self-confidence and competency scores after completing two chemotherapy administration simulations and debriefing sessions. Going forward, this DNP author will continue to track the number of medication errors related to chemotherapy in the following months to see if the rate declines. The oncology leadership team will then determine if chemotherapy administration simulations should permanently become part of the facility's chemotherapy certification policy. Finally, this DNP project may have been done on a small scale, but is an example of a change

that can easily be adapted to other practice settings. It is a practice change that has the potential to improve patient outcomes in one of our more vulnerable populations.

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Appendix A

Permission to Use the Lewin's Model

HomeHelpEmail SupportJoanne Mulvaney ▾

Unfreezing change as three steps: Rethinking Kurt Lewin's legacy for change management

Author: Stephen Cummings, Todd Bridgman, Kenneth G Brown

Publication: Human Relations

Publisher: SAGE Publications

Date: 01/01/2016

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Appendix B

Chemotherapy and Immunotherapy Certification Course Using Simulation Flyer

Chemotherapy & Immunotherapy Course

Purpose: Improve nursing confidence and competency through the use of simulation

- Simulations:
- Managing Side Effects
- Unit Based Chemotherapy Update
- Immunotherapy

Enroll for one of the classes scheduled through API using code: 4CA00205		
November 2020	0800-1200	Simulation Center, McMillen Building

Talks from Lead Nurses, Oncology Pharmacists, and Nurse Educator!

***Mandatory for Chemo Certified Nurses in 2020**

 TORRANCE MEMORIAL
A CEDARS-SINAI AFFILIATE

Appendix C

Email with Course Information

Hello oncology nurses,

First of all, congratulations on completing your ONS Chemotherapy/Immunotherapy Certification Card! The Oncology Services Leadership Team and Cancer Committee are excited to watch your oncology knowledge and expertise grow.

Administering Chemotherapy and Immunotherapy is complex, freighting and can be unsafe. To better assist your transition to a competent chemotherapy certified registered nurse, the Cancer Committee led by the Oncology Services director, Nancy Lean, are mandating all newly certified nurses of 2020 to participate in a 4-hour review course that will consist of simulations. Simulations has been proven to be beneficial in practicing new skills and it will allow everyone to practice if a safe environment. I have spoken on the current change as part of my DNP project in hopes to grow your confidence and competence when caring for our adult cancer patients. I will collect data on your confidence and competence, but it will not include any names.

Attached is the flyer for the mandated course that you will get paid for through the elective education funds.

The lead nurses, Oncology Pharmacist, myself and the Cancer Committee are looking forward to this class!

Thank you and please contact me for any questions,

Joanne Mulvaney MSN-Ed, RN, OCN

Oncology/Med-Surg Advanced Clinical Nurse Educator

Appendix D

Approval Letter to Implement DNP Project at Site

April 27, 2020

Rachel Maclanahan, DNP, RN, PHN, NCSN
DNP Consortium Coordinator
California State University, Fullerton: School of Nursing, EC-190, Attn: DNP
800 N. State College Blvd.
Fullerton, California 92831

Dear Dr. Maclanahan,

The purpose of this letter of agreement is to show our support relating to our employer Joanne Mulvaney, MSN-Ed, RN, OCN. We are aware that she is pursuing her Doctor of Nursing Practice, with a deliverable in the form of a unique project for degree obtainment.

The organization is aware of Joanne Mulvaney's need to perform her quality improvement project of implementing simulation as part of the chemotherapy certification process for the facility's oncology nurses. She is receiving direct support from myself and our Oncology Services Department. We look forward to her project and its results.

Sincerely,

A black rectangular redaction box covering the signature of Nancy Lean.

Nancy Lean, MSN, MHSA, RN, NEA-BC
Director, Medical/Oncology Services
Hunt Cancer Institute
Torrance Memorial Medical Center
310-517-1217 office
714-267-1692 cell

Appendix E

Letter of Request to Implement DNP Project at Site

Date: March 30, 2020

To: Nancy Lean

3330 Lomita Blvd.

Torrance, CA 90505

CC:

From: Joanne Mulvaney

Re: Doctorate of Nursing Practice Project

Use of Simulation for Chemotherapy Competency Training

As part of the Doctorate of Nursing Practice, candidates complete a culminating project. A synopsis of my project follows:

Background: The National Institute for Occupational Safety and Health has identified chemotherapy as a high-alert and hazardous drug. Accordingly, the American Society of Clinical Oncology (ASCO) and the Oncology Nursing Society (ONS) (2013) have developed chemotherapy administration standards related to safe use. Although cancer treatments including chemotherapy have significantly prolonged the lifespan of oncology patients, the administration of these toxic yet lifesaving agents require extensive knowledge and experience to ensure safe care (Carreon et al., 2015). Previously, nurses were certified in a classroom environment with hands on experience through ONS. This shift in the certification process has negatively affected nursing confidence and potentially competency. Nurses newly certified in chemotherapy administration have reported a lack of confidence and competence when administering chemotherapy drugs. During 2018 and 2019, an increase in chemotherapy medication errors related to wrong route, incorrect administration and delayed administration of rescue medication for hypersensitivity reactions was observed. A significant finding was that each of these adverse events had been made by a nurse who had been newly certified within that past year. In communicating with these nurses, there were reports of feeling anxious when receiving assignments that included administering chemotherapy, as they were worried about making a mistake that would harm their patients.

Purpose: The purpose of this Doctor of Nursing Practice (DNP) project is to increase nurse self-efficacy and competence when administering chemotherapy drugs at an acute care hospital, by including simulation as part of the chemotherapy certification process for Torrance Memorial's oncology nurses.

Methods: A team of stakeholders will be identified with an interest in improving the chemotherapy certification process. The current process will be reviewed with a focus on opportunities for improving confidence and competency. Simulations will be incorporated as part of the TMMC's chemotherapy course in summer of 2020. This new strategy will be evaluated immediately, 30 days and 60 days after the course. Confidence and competence will be evaluated with appropriate measures. The team of stakeholders will continue to meet and evaluate the need for revisions to the process.

Deliverables: 1. Revised TMMC's chemotherapy certification policy. 2. Educational materials related to the chemotherapy course. 3. Standardized process to ensure sustainability of the new process change including metrics to measure self-efficacy and competency. 4. Presentation of project outcomes to stakeholders and nursing staff.

American Society of Clinical Oncology and Oncology Nursing Society. (2013). *ASCO/ONS chemotherapy administration safety standards*. <http://bit.ly/18fDeeu>.

Carreon, N., Sugarman, C., Beener, E., & Agan, D. (2015). Creating and standardizing annual chemotherapy competencies throughout a healthcare system. *Journal for Nurses in Professional Development*, 31, 35-39.

Appendix F

Simulation Scenarios

Patient History: E.M. is a 68-year old man recently diagnosed with non-Hodgkin lymphoma. He is a Vietnam War veteran and was exposed to Agent Orange during his time there. He is being admitted for his first cycle of R-EPOCH. The schedule for R-EPOCH is 1 cycle every 21 days. E.M. will be admitted for each cycle of therapy. He is classified as a stage IV(B) and has no significant comorbidities. E.M.'s vital signs include a heart rate (HR) of 72 bpm, blood pressure (BP) of 124/74, respiratory rate (RR) of 16, a 98.6°F temperature (T), and 100% oxygen saturation (O₂ Sat) on room air.

Scenario 1: Nurse will be administering Rituximab.

E.M.'s dose of Rituximab has been increased to 100 mg per hour over 30 minutes. E.M. says "my stomach kind of hurts" and "I am feeling cold. Can I have another blanket?" Patient starts shake and demonstrate rigors.

Vitals: HR=140 bpm, BP=88/58, RR=24, T=101.5 °F, O₂ Sat=92%

Scenario 2: Nurse will be administering Cyclophosphamide.

E.M. asks nurse "How long is this going to take? I am feeling sick and I think I need to throw up. Give me a bucket I need to throw up!"

Vitals: HR=80 bpm, BP=110/60, RR=24, T=98.6 °F, O₂ Sat=98%

Appendix G

Needed Equipment and Budget Costs for Simulation Training Program

1. Clinical Simulation Skills Tech

Pay Rate approximately \$30.00 per hour → 30 x 6 hours = \$180.00.

2. Four content experts' competency evaluation training

Pay rate approximately \$60.00 per hour for 4 members → (60 x 2) x 4 = \$480.00

3. Needed Supplies

Personal protective equipment (24 people)

Expired chemotherapy spills kit (12 count)

Gauze pads (2 packs)

Copies of the chemotherapy orders (24 count)

Expired IV fluids bag with red food coloring (3 count)

Expired normal saline IV bag (12 count)

Expired IV Tubing/Set up (24 count)

Alaris pumps and IV Poles (3 count)

Expired syringes labeled: Benadryl, Demerol, Morphine, Solu-Cortef, Epinephrine (15 count)

= approximately \$109.00

Appendix H

NLN Student Satisfaction and Self-Confidence in Learning Survey

Student Satisfaction and Self-Confidence in Learning

Instructions: This questionnaire is a series of statements about your personal attitudes about the instruction you receive during your simulation activity. Each item represents a statement about your attitude toward your satisfaction with learning and self-confidence in obtaining the instruction you need. There are no right or wrong answers. You will probably agree with some of the statements and disagree with others. Please indicate your own personal feelings about each statement below by marking the numbers that best describe your attitude or beliefs. Please be truthful and describe your attitude as it really is, not what you would like for it to be. This is anonymous with the results being compiled as a group, not individually.

Mark:

- 1 = STRONGLY DISAGREE with the statement
- 2 = DISAGREE with the statement
- 3 = UNDECIDED - you neither agree or disagree with the statement
- 4 = AGREE with the statement
- 5 = STRONGLY AGREE with the statement

Satisfaction with Current Learning	SD	D	UN	A	SA
1. The teaching methods used in this simulation were helpful and effective.	<input type="radio"/> 1	<input type="radio"/> 2	<input type="radio"/> 3	<input type="radio"/> 4	<input type="radio"/> 5
2. The simulation provided me with a variety of learning materials and activities to promote my learning the medical surgical curriculum.	<input type="radio"/> 1	<input type="radio"/> 2	<input type="radio"/> 3	<input type="radio"/> 4	<input type="radio"/> 5
3. I enjoyed how my instructor taught the simulation.	<input type="radio"/> 1	<input type="radio"/> 2	<input type="radio"/> 3	<input type="radio"/> 4	<input type="radio"/> 5
4. The teaching materials used in this simulation were motivating and helped me to learn.	<input type="radio"/> 1	<input type="radio"/> 2	<input type="radio"/> 3	<input type="radio"/> 4	<input type="radio"/> 5
5. The way my instructor(s) taught the simulation was suitable to the way I learn.	<input type="radio"/> 1	<input type="radio"/> 2	<input type="radio"/> 3	<input type="radio"/> 4	<input type="radio"/> 5
Self-confidence in Learning	SD	D	UN	A	SA
6. I am confident that I am mastering the content of the simulation activity that my instructors presented to me.	<input type="radio"/> 1	<input type="radio"/> 2	<input type="radio"/> 3	<input type="radio"/> 4	<input type="radio"/> 5
7. I am confident that this simulation covered critical content necessary for the mastery of medical surgical curriculum.	<input type="radio"/> 1	<input type="radio"/> 2	<input type="radio"/> 3	<input type="radio"/> 4	<input type="radio"/> 5
8. I am confident that I am developing the skills and obtaining the required knowledge from this simulation to perform necessary tasks in a clinical setting	<input type="radio"/> 1	<input type="radio"/> 2	<input type="radio"/> 3	<input type="radio"/> 4	<input type="radio"/> 5
9. My instructors used helpful resources to teach the simulation.	<input type="radio"/> 1	<input type="radio"/> 2	<input type="radio"/> 3	<input type="radio"/> 4	<input type="radio"/> 5
10. It is my responsibility as the student to learn what I need to know from this simulation activity.	<input type="radio"/> 1	<input type="radio"/> 2	<input type="radio"/> 3	<input type="radio"/> 4	<input type="radio"/> 5
11. I know how to get help when I do not understand the concepts covered in the simulation.	<input type="radio"/> 1	<input type="radio"/> 2	<input type="radio"/> 3	<input type="radio"/> 4	<input type="radio"/> 5
12. I know how to use simulation activities to learn critical aspects of these skills.	<input type="radio"/> 1	<input type="radio"/> 2	<input type="radio"/> 3	<input type="radio"/> 4	<input type="radio"/> 5
13. It is the instructor's responsibility to tell me what I need to learn of the simulation activity content during class time..	<input type="radio"/> 1	<input type="radio"/> 2	<input type="radio"/> 3	<input type="radio"/> 4	<input type="radio"/> 5

Appendix I

Permission to Reproduce/Use NLN Student Satisfaction and Self-Confidence in Learning

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Eau Claire, Wisconsin
May 2, 2020
- ▶ NLN Faculty Intensive Week 2020
Jun 1 - 5, 2020
- ▶ Applied Data Analysis for Nursing Education Researchers
Jun 8, 2020
- ▶ Advancing the Science of Nursing Education Through Research
Jun 9 - 10, 2020

Appendix J

Chemotherapy/Immunotherapy Administration Competency Verification Form

Competency Verification Form CHEMOTHERAPY IMMUNOTHERAPY ADMINISTRATION

Staff Name: _____

Drug Name: Simulation 1) _____ Type of infusion: _____

Simulation 2) _____ Type of infusion: _____

0=Not met 1=Met

Anything less than 1 for simulation requires a plan to re-educate/train employee and documentation of reevaluation of competency.

	Sim 1	Sim 2
1. Reviews administration guidelines and drug indications on oncology drug reference.		
2. Ascertains adequate laboratory values and computes ANC		
3. Obtains patient height, weight and computes BSA		
4. Documents correct calculations on pharmacy oncology worksheet.		
5. With another RN, checks drug label for correct drug, dose, route and patient compared to original MD order.		
6. Verifies patient identity by checking two approved patient identifiers.		
7. Provides and ensures appropriate patient education.		
8. Measures and records baseline vital signs.		
9. Verifies patient allergy history.		
10. Ensures the availability of extravasation kit, medications indicated for allergic reaction, spill kit, and crash cart		
11. Gathers necessary equipment and supplies		
12. Washes hands and dons gloves and appropriate PPE		
13. Establishes peripheral IV or accesses CVC		
14. Verbalizes rationale for premedication(s) & administers as indicated		
15. Verbalizes signs and symptoms of hypersensitivity and evidenced-based interventions		
16. Administers agent over ordered time and with correct equipment		
17. Checks patient condition and status of IV site throughout drug administration.		
18. Ensures drug containment at all times.		
19. Flushes with compatible IV solution at the end of infusion		
20. Identifies nursing management of specific agent side effects, risks and complications.		
21. Communicates changes in patient status to the appropriate healthcare team member.		
22. Demonstrates safe handling and disposal of agent(s)		
23. Documents medication administration according to policy.		
24. Assesses patient reaction and documents accurately.		

Evaluator Printed Name: _____ Signature: _____ Date: _____

Appendix K

Table K

Table K

Table of the Comparison of the Oncology Nurses' Self-Confidence Pre- and Post-Simulation

	Confidence Score Pre-Simulations	Confidence Score Post-Simulations	0 = no improvement 1 = improvement
Nurse 1	36	40	1
Nurse 2	32	40	1
Nurse 3	30	36	1
Nurse 4	30	31	1
Nurse 5	38	40	1
Nurse 6	30	40	1
Nurse 7	33	40	1
Nurse 8	29	40	1
Nurse 9	37	38	1
Nurse 10	36	38	1
Nurse 11	32	40	1
			Total: 11

Appendix L

Figure L

Figure L

Bar Graph of the Nurses' Self-Confidence Pre- and Post-Simulation

Appendix M

Table M

Table M

Table of the Comparison of the Oncology Nurse's Competency Score Simulation One and Simulation Two

	Competency Assessment Simulation Score 1	Competency Assessment Simulation Score 1	0 = no improvement 1 = improvement
Nurse 1	16	24	1
Nurse 2	20	24	1
Nurse 3	12	24	1
Nurse 4	18	24	1
Nurse 5	20	24	1
Nurse 6	22	24	1
Nurse 7	22	24	1
Nurse 8	18	24	1
Nurse 9	20	24	1
Nurse 10	21	24	1
Nurse 11	23	24	1
			Total: 11

Appendix N

Figure N

Figure N

Bar Graph of the Nurses' Competency Scores Simulation One and Simulation Two

